

Supplementary Information

Shaping a gallium alloy and an ionic liquid into spherical mirrors for future liquid-based telescopes – experimental setup and demonstration in parabolic flights

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Additional files provided in the Supplementary Information:

- PF 2022 - experimental log.pdf – a table listing all the experiments performed on the flights.
- Gallium filling (with captions).mp4 – a video showing the process of filling gallium into a capsule under vacuum.

1. Optical design

Fig. S1(a) shows the optical train design in Zemax. **Fig. S1(a)** describes the system prescription, where the optical fiber is represented as an on-axis point source and the mirror under test (MUT) is modeled as a paraxial lens. **Fig. S1(b)** presents a schematic of the optical train for the case where the focal length of the MUT is 165 mm. The optimization tool in Zemax was used to find values for the thickness of surfaces #1 and #5, so that the MUT plane would be conjugated to the SH plane with minimal wavefront error.

(a)

	Surface Type	Comment	Radius	Thickness	Material	Coating	Clear Semi-Dia	Chip Zone	Mech Semi-Dia
0	OBJECT	Standard ▾	Infinity	Infinity			Infinity U	0.000	Infinity
1	STOP	Paraxial ▾		191.278			20.000 U	-	-
2	(aper)	Standard ▾	TRI 1 28.770	5.200	N-F2	THORA	12.700 U	0.000	12.700
3	(aper)	Standard ▾	TRI 2 13.333	19.800	N-K5	THORA	12.700 U	0.000	12.700
4	(aper)	Standard ▾	TRI 3 -13.333	5.200	N-F2	THORA	12.700 U	0.000	12.700
5	(aper)	Standard ▾	TRI 4 -28.770	38.967 U			12.700 U	0.000	12.700
6		Standard ▾	SHWS Infinity	-1489.013			5.500 U	0.000	5.500
7	IMAGE	Standard ▾	Infinity	-			104.132	0.000	104.132

(c) MUT

Fig. S1 Optical train design from Zemax. (a) The prescription table showing the information for all the surfaces. (b) A schematic of the ray tracing through the optical train, in the case where the focal length of the MUT is 165 mm.

2. Uncertainty analysis

We here describe the approach for estimation our measurement uncertainties. We start by accounting for the uncertainty in the raw wavefront data – this would be a root-mean-square of the accuracy provided by the manufacturer $\delta w_{SH} = 0.02 \mu m$, and the additional wavefront error

introduced by the relay – simulated and measured to be no more than $\delta w_{relay} = \lambda / 2$ at 590 nm,

hence the uncertainty in the raw wavefront can be estimated to be $\delta w = \sqrt{\delta w_{SH}^2 + \delta w_{relay}^2}$.

This uncertainty propagates through the analysis and affects all the quantities we estimate – the radius of curvature of the wavefront, the focal length of the reference paraboloid and the irregularity of the final surface. We here detail the computational of this propagation, accounting for possible correlation between fitting parameters. In every fit we seek to find the optimal parameter vector $\vec{x} = [x_0 \quad x_1 \quad \dots \quad x_{N_p-1}]$ such that a cost function, in the form of the chi squared estimator,

$$\chi^2(\vec{x}) = \frac{1}{N_d - N_p - 1} \sum_{i=0}^{N_d-1} \sqrt{\left(\frac{f_{m,i}(\vec{x}) - f_{d,i}}{\delta f_{d,i}} \right)^2}, \quad (\text{S1})$$

will be minimized. N_d is the number of data points, N_p is the number of fitted parameters, $f_d(\vec{x})$ is the model function, f_d are the data points and δf_d is the uncertainty in f_d . Once the optimal solution for \vec{x} is found, the correlated errors in the parameter vector $\delta \vec{x}$ can be computed through the covariance matrix formalism¹. Assuming the parameter errors distribute normally (a common assumption¹), we calculate the hessian of χ^2 ,

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial^2(\chi^2) / \partial x_0^2 & \dots & \partial^2(\chi^2) / \partial x_0 \partial x_{N_p-1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \partial^2(\chi^2) / \partial x_0^2 & \dots & \partial^2(\chi^2) / \partial x_0^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{S2})$$

and its inverse, also known as the ‘curvature matrix’,

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{H}^{-1}. \quad (\text{S3})$$

The correlated error in parameter x_j (which accounts for variability in all parameters simultaneously) is

$$\delta x_{j,corr} = E_{jj}^2. \quad (S4)$$

The uncertainty is then the correlated error multiplied by a coefficient determined by the confidence level and number of parameters being fitted,

$$\delta x_j = \delta x_{j,corr} \cdot \sqrt{C}. \quad (S5)$$

The value for C can be found in section 15.6 in Press et al¹. For example, for four parameters and 95% confidence, $C = 9.72$.

This method allows us to propagate the measurement error δw through the regression analysis and estimate the uncertainties in the radii of curvature of the sphere fit R . To estimate the uncertainty in the focal length δf , we take the resulting error in the wavefront radius of curvature δR (as explained above), and multiply it by the sensitivity of the focal length estimation to changes in that radius,

$$\delta f = \frac{\partial f(R)}{\partial R} \delta R, \quad (S6)$$

where $f(R)$ is a mapping between the wavefront radius of curvature and the focal length of the MUT, tabulated by ray tracing simulation of the optical train in Zemax.

3. Estimation of coordinate displacement error

When converting wavefront error into topographic deviations in Eq. (9), we have neglected the lateral displacements of the reflected beams when crossing the mirror surface – i.e., we note that in Eq (9), $\Delta\phi$, z , and z^* are evaluated at the same $x-y$ coordinates, although in reality $\Delta\phi$

should be evaluated at slightly different locations, $\Delta\phi(x + \delta x, y + \delta y)$, where δx and δy are schematically shown in Fig. 5 as the lengths AC and AC^* . δx and δy are themselves spatial functions, can be expressed in terms of the surface geometry as

$$\delta x(x, y) = \cos \left(\arctan \left(\frac{dz/dy}{dz/dx} \right) \right) \cdot \tan \beta \cdot (H - z) \quad (\text{S7})$$

and

$$\delta y(x, y) = \sin \left(\arctan \left(\frac{dz/dy}{dz/dx} \right) \right) \cdot \tan \beta \cdot (H - z). \quad (\text{S8})$$

From a Taylor series expansion, the error in the $\Delta\phi$ term in Eq. (9) is thus on the order of

$\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \delta x + \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial y} \delta y$. This must be compared with the discretization error of the SH sensor, which reports

the average wavefront over a pixel with dimensions Δx and Δy . This reported value is regarded as representing the phase value at the center of the pixel, and this discretization error is on the

order of $\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \Delta x + \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial y} \Delta y$. In our system, the SH pixel size, $\Delta x = \Delta y = 600 \mu m$, whereas evaluation

of equations (S7) and (S8) for our mirrors yields a maximum of $\delta x, \delta y \sim 15 \mu m$. Thus, the error

due to approximation of $x \approx x + \delta x$ and $y \approx y + \delta y$ in Eq. (9) is negligible.

References

1. W. H. Press et al., *Numerical Recipes: The Art of Scientific Computing*, 3rd ed., in *Numerical Recipes - The Art of Scientific Computing*, 3rd ed., Cambridge Press, New York (2007) [doi:10.1137/1031025].